

Understanding Hi-story: Literariness, Historicity and How the Narratives of Revolution Changed Hands in Bengal

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This article begins by acknowledging the relationship between history and story; both of them are denoted by a common term in French, which is *histoire*. I want to refer to the narratives which constitute the history of the revolutionary nationalism as *histoire*, as acts which became stories which were told and consumed with great interest and they were also history, in the sense that they were “truths of the events”. And here I use the term “event” with the connotations derived from Alain Badiou's definition of *event*. Daniel Bensaïd comments,

This is why, contrary to Kant, for whom the truth and universal relevance of the French Revolution was to be found in the enthusiastic and disinterested gaze of its onlookers, for Badiou, the truth of the event is that of its participants: it should be sought for or listened to in the living words uttered by Robespierre or Saint-Just, rather than in the detached commentaries produced by Furet and the Thermidorian historians; in the tragic decisions made by Lenin (and Trotsky), rather than the judgments made out of harm's way by Hélène Carrère d'Encausse and Stéphane Courtois. (marxists.org)

Secondly, while the relationship between fictionality and historicity will be my area of investigation, the raw materials for this investigation will be taken from the stories and histories of revolutionary nationalism which concern, among other luminaries, the three stalwarts of this movement, Bankim, Vivekananda and Subhash (they succeeded each other in a politico-philosophical sense), and also from the narratives which are imprinted with the nuances of the transformation of this movement through communistic proselytizing activities, as well as the nationalist critiques and resistances

against such activities. I am not going to chronicle the communists' subversion of the national revolutionary movement, and I am not going to chronicle the communists' glorification of their out-maneuvrings of the then existing national revolutionary movement. While trying to understand the stories and the histories of Bengal's revolutionary movement by their mutual inter-references, I would rather take an odd attempt or two to blast open the dreary continuum of history as Terry Eagleton has preferred to do on some occasions (most notably in *Walter Benjamin* and *Saints and Scholars*). The familiar colloquial expression of “making history” suggests an action that a culture and a community of people collectively celebrate throughout their history, and that action enters collective consciousness, collective memory as a distinguishing milestone, as an *event*. Needless to say, there are cultural yardsticks which will determine what constitutes the requirements for the making of history for a certain community. What is an event in the Bengalis' history may not be an event for Assam, and vice versa, as history is communally delimited.

The relationship between history and story (narrative/art/literature) works at multiple levels. Historical fiction in Bengal is well established as a genre that began with Bankim Chandra. Secondly, fictionalised history (different from historical fiction) is a popular format and just like popular science it offers documentary-fiction, and as a classic example of that we have Sailesh Dey's *Ami Subhash Bolchi (This is Subhash Speaking)*. In recent times, Shankar's *Ami Vivekananda Bolchi (This is Vivekananda Speaking)* is a specimen that falls within this genre. Thirdly, history can be made by stories as well, so the novels of Bankim which created nationalist history, like *Anandamath* did, constitutes another category; stories which gave birth to history. A similar example from abroad is the Russian novel *What is to be Done* by Nikolai Chernyshevsky (Lenin, who was a lifelong admirer of Chernyshevsky, took the title of his eponymous history-making treatise from this novel). Another category, the fourth one includes the plethora of narratives and legends and stories/songs/poems which accompanied the *events* of revolutionary nationalism, for instance Sharatchandra's *Pother Dabi*

(*The Demand of the Path*), and the revolutionary songs and poems of Nazrul Islam (both the writers were actively involved with the revolutionaries); later on, similar narratives were made to describe the continuity, legacy and heritage of the revolutionary nationalist movement as inherited by the communist party. We shall see how these narratives worked since the national revolutionary movement started in Bengal and when the revolutionaries were converted inside British prisons, how that was culturally defended by telling a story of telos, a grand narrative of revolution (the communists' telos is a grand narrative of history with a sufficient amount of determinism that can forecast a linear progression of history; no doubt it was a product of the Enlightenment triumphalism in its teleology) that argued that giving up nationalism was the next required step in history for the revolution to succeed.

In response to the noted anti-nationalist historian Eric Hobsbawm's evocation of the vintage authority of a statement made by Ernest Renan in a spirit of castigating nationalist historiography from an empiricist perspective, "Getting its history wrong is part of being a nation" (Hobsbawm 12), I would rather point out that being a non-nation is still a way (perhaps a bigger and worse way) of getting our history wrong. One can evoke Bankim Chandra to point out that there is no hi-story without subjective perspectives; as Bankim said: "Read in childhood fables that a man drew a painting. The painting depicts that a man is beating a lion with a shoe. The painter man called a lion to see the painting. The lion said that if lions knew how to draw, the painting would have been of a different kind. Bengalis never wrote history. That is why the historical painting of the Bengalis is in such conditions" (2: 295). Terry Eagleton points out in his one of his studies on Irish culture (*Heathcliff and the Great Hunger*) that like a person, a nation should be able to tell a convincing story about itself: "A nation, like an individual, has to be able to recount a reasonable story of itself, one without either despair or presumption. As long as it veers between idealization on the one hand and disapproval on the other, it will behave exactly like Freud's neurotic patient, afflicted by reminiscences"

(ix). Eagleton's comment establishes a relation between nationalism and subjectivity. It also alludes to the idea that either to idealize or to disapprove nationalism would both be a neurotic condition, and the sensible approach would be to receive and analyse the memories of nationalism in our conscious mind without letting them haunt our unconscious. As stories are never neutral, and they are always told from perspectives, therefore a subjective story-telling is an indispensable process of interpretation that the bare facts perceived by human agencies would have to undergo. Eminent historian E H Carr believed it to be an illusion that history was made up of bare data. Carr observes, "It used to be said that facts speak for themselves. This is, of course, untrue. The facts speak only when the historian calls on them: it is he who decides to which facts to give the floor, and in what order or context. It was, I think, one of Pirandello's characters who said that a fact is like a sack - it won't stand up till you've put something in it" (11). While Carr chronicles the battle between older empiricists and historicists (the former pushing for neutrality and objectivity of facts, the latter for historical conditionality, subjectivity and relativity) with his opinion in favor of the latter, he rules out disinterestedness and gives his vote in favor of the historians' agenda, choice, and politics which come to interpret the facts. And it is quite interesting that he lifts an example from literature to elaborate his point. It further alludes to the literariness of history, (literary, in the sense of something imaginary, was a Romantic invention; but in the older, original sense, literary was something that was written down in a special way, with alphabetic *letters*; history, science and philosophy all qualified as literature and today, the same sense of literature is retained in various other fields outside the academic discipline of "Literature"), and the narratives which constitute history. History is an interpretation of facts.

However, a fetishization of the literary mapping of the historical process is not on the present writer's agenda. First of all, the strict separation of literariness from historicity is an aspect of the

reification, commoditization and compartmentalization for which capitalist modernity is renowned. In fact, as if as a challenge to this strict division, many contemporary writers like Salman Rushdie, Amitav Ghosh (who are remarkably fascinated with historicity) today deliberately attempt a juxtaposition of historical research and fictionality in their works. Thus, such works become conscious and self-reflexive sites of merger and exchange between literariness and historicity. Secondly, the composite process of “history-making” has to be conceived in its organic whole as far as possible. Instead of going for the empiricist's fantasy of absolute and pure history constituted of unadulterated neutral impersonal data (a fantasy derived directly from Enlightenment rationality), a postmodern approach would no doubt prefer an engagement with the studies of human subjectivity, narrativity and myth making in the composite recording process of history.

Eminent Historian Ramesh Chandra Majumdar wrote in a letter (dated 26 November 1965) to Sharadindu Bandyopadhyay, after reading his historical romance *Tungabhadrar Teere* (“On the Banks of Tungabhadra”),

You have portrayed the memory of the past grandeur of Vijayanagar through a pleasant narrative – for this reason we, the historians are extremely grateful – because people do not read history – but they will read your book. The objective with which Alexander Dumas wrote novels like *The Three Musketeers*, a similar purpose will be served through your two novels (note: here R C Majumdar is referring to *Gouda Mallar* and *Tungabhadrar Teere*) regarding post-Shashanka Bengal and the Vijayanagar of Deva Raya.” (Bandyopadhyay 616)

R C Majumdar's letter is an acknowledgment of the role of literary works in propagating historical literacy, as well as the intellectual juxtaposition of literariness and historicity within the discourse of

nationalism. Clearly, as their respective attachments to nationalist thought are well known, here was one nationalist writer (a Historian) talking to another nationalist writer (a Novelist). One kind of writing interactively complements another in the process of making nationalist consciousness.

An example of literary celebration of nationalist history coming to my mind is Terry Eagleton's novel *Saints and Scholars* that has the legendary Irish leader James Connolly (a socialist revolutionary leader of the failed Easter uprising of 1916) as its protagonist. Here is how Eagleton ends his novel, with the description of Connolly's execution by the British firing squad: "As the rifles were raised he was already fading, dwindling, fragments of his body flaking away to leave only an image beneath. When the bullets reached him, he would disappear entirely into myth, his body nothing but a piece of language, the first cry of the new republic" (145). So the executed body of Connolly becomes a piece of *language* as his corporeality turns into a myth. Connolly's execution is an event that makes history and is celebrated in narratives. Elsewhere, Eagleton evokes the noted Marxist thinker and Jewish mystic Walter Benjamin to emphasize the role of the narratives in giving justice to the departed, and in preserving their memory, and in celebrating their presence by means of revolutionary imagination

[As per Walter Benjamin,] it remains the harsh truth that the dead can be raised only in revolutionary imagination. There is no literal way in which we can compensate them for the sufferings they received at the hands of the ruling order. We cannot recall the crushed medieval peasantry or the wage-slaves of early industrial capitalism, the children who died afraid and unloved in the wretched hovels of class society, the women who broke their backs for regimes which used them with arrogance and contempt, the colonized nations which collapsed under an oppressor who found them at once sinister and charming. There is no literal way in which the shades of these dead can be summoned to claim justice from those who abused them. The

pastness of the past is the simple truth that, rewrite and recuperate them as we may, the wretched of history have passed away, and will not share in any more compassionate social order we may be able to create. (1998: 325)

Remembering those who died is usually a highly politicized act. We shall see that the Bengal communists would consistently claim the legacy of the revolutionaries, and if we examine the narrative formation process at the moment when the nationalist revolutionary movement was being metamorphosed into communist movement we may be able to locate various disjuncture and punctures in the stories which have since been told by the communists, forever willing to project themselves as the sole inheritors and torch-bearers of the revolutionary movement. Late Saibal Mitra, a noted Bengali writer (and an erstwhile Naxalite leader) wrote in the late forties/early fifties while he was in his teenage, “O brother of Khudiram, cross the sea of darkness/ Comrade Stalin and China's Chou En Lai are showing you the light”, as is reported by his classmate, Samaresh Majumdar (himself a renowned writer) in a memoir (Majumdar 26). In the same vein, Majumdar records that the general atmosphere among the young students was heavily tilted in favour of the communist party; Mitra told his classmates that “unless one reads Karl Marx and Mao Ze Dong, the eyes that perceive life are not opened” (Majumdar 26). Saibal Mitra in his teenage had a book of poems to his name, titled *Khudho Swadesh (Agitated Homeland)*, which according to Majumdar belonged to the genre of communist revolutionary poetry, established in Bengal by Sukanta Bhattacharya, a poet who died very young in the early forties. Sukanta remained an ideal for the leftist poets through generations. The title of Mitra's book *Khudho Swadesh* is taken from a poem of Sukanta. Interestingly, Sukanta himself wrote the following lines about the Nationalist Revolutionaries:

“They were brave, they used to brew storms in heavens

Their stories, (written) with the blood of the foreign oppressors

(Written) with bullets, guns and fire of bombs

Are thrilling even today!”

This poem records the history-making acts of the revolutionary nationalists, and makes an explicit celebration of their stories (“kahini”). By recording these acts in such an inspiring literary language (my translation is a rather weak reproduction of the original rhymed poem in Bengali), Sukanta's poem itself entered into the lore of revolution, and became an idiomatic literary expression that continued to capture the popular imagination about Ognijug. These lines became a rallying point of reference whenever other writers wanted to evoke the fiery *events* of national revolutionary movement. The legacy of the national revolutionaries continued to be claimed by the Naxalite movement, following the practice of undivided Communist Party's evocation of the memory of the heroes. Even after fifty years, Sukanta's poem makes an appearance in Nabarun Bhattacharya's (a writer known for his Naxalite sympathies) Sahitya Academy award winning novel, *Herbert*, in an episode where a father alights the pyre of his Naxalite son (murdered in police custody) and recites these lines as his son's body is being cremated. A policeman standing nearby whispers to his colleague, “look there, father of the Naxalite is uttering a mantra because his son is burning!” (Bhattacharya 34).

A mantra is a part of the collective lore that bestows signification on human life and death, and its ritualistic function is to tell a story of cosmic significance, and in these aspects it resembles the heroic *events* of revolutionary struggle. There were characteristics of popular, heroic and legendary narratives in the historical achievements of Revolutionary nationalism. Shobhanlal Mukherjee, a retired professor from Kolkata whose father was a colleague of Charles Tegart, the police commissioner of Kolkata (widely known for his brutal suppression of the revolutionary

movement) reminisces in an article published in *The Statesman*, “Tegart had once told his colleagues that if Jatin were an Englishman, then the English people would have built his statue next to Nelson’s at Trafalgar Square. In his note to JE Francis of the India Office in 1926, he described Bengali terrorists as “the most selfless political workers in India”” (Mukherjee).

The epic quality in the acts and accomplishments of the revolutionaries of Bengal and their acts which made history and entered popular memory are constitutive of *histoire*. These events were ingrained into popular memory. Communistic propaganda made use of that memory, while neither Congress nor the mainstream Hindu politics had a corresponding revolutionary temperament/ideology/agenda to lay a claim to that memory. However, this was a reworked memory that the communists evoked. It was reworked from the perspective of the communists. Works like Sudhanshu Dasgupta's *Karagare Communist Howar Kahini* and *Andaman Jail theke Muzaffar Ahmad Bhavan* (*The Story of Being a Communist in the Prison* and *From Andaman Jail to Muzaffar Ahmed Bhavan*; Muzaffar Ahmed Bhavan is the Bengal CPIM headquarters) perpetrate this story that the revolutionaries chose Marxism because it was a scientific doctrine, indispensable for carrying forward the revolutionary momentum. In reality, the superior scientific credentials of Marxism were put to the use of subversion of nationalism, as we shall see later in this article: the neophytes were motivated by their party (that was in turn instructed by its Soviet bosses to collaborate with the British) to surrender the national interest under the guise of internationalism.

No one can deny that at that time, the Communist movement was at its charming best; those were its heydays. The mouthpiece of M N Roy's Communist Party in exile, titled *Vanguard* (so titled from 15 May 1923 onwards; first published as *Vanguard of the Indian Independence* in 1922), which made a clear mention of its affiliation with the Communist International in Moscow on its front page, was regularly posted to Pratul Ganguly (who was included in Roy's mailing list at Muzaffar Ahmed's

behest) of Anushilan Samity whose activists once taunted the Jugantar boys belonging to Jiban Chatterjee's group, "We have connection with the Communist International. So these magazines are coming to us. Why, they never come to you." Then Jugantar boys spoke of their resentment to their leader Jiban Chatterjee who in turn requested Muzaffar Ahmed not to exclude their group from *Vanguard's* mailing list. Muzaffar Ahmed obliged readily (as he notes with some pleasure and satisfaction in his autobiography) and henceforth Jiban Chatterjee's Jugantar group was added to the list of postal recipients of *Vanguard* (Ghosh: 1987: 44).

Conversions to communism could have been facilitated by some inherent problems of the revolutionary movement; for instance, the caste question. Pulin Bihari Das's autobiography mentions Hemchandra Das Kanungo's (Mahishya by caste) frustration over the caste-ridden, Brahmin-Baidya-Kayastha dominated bhadralok society of Kolkata revolutionaries (333). It may not be entirely gratuitous for me to mention here that the Mahishya caste is considered to be the founders of the renowned dynasty of the Ganga kings of Orissa, according to noted Oriya scholar Harihar Kanungo (orissa.gov.in). The *artificial* caste hierarchy of Bengal (a handiwork of the Sen kings) and the social inequality of the traditional Hindu society were not sufficiently addressed by most revolutionary nationalist thinkers, barring a few exceptions. But the Indian Communist movement offered an imaginary solution to the problems of caste. In effect, Indian communism has become an idealizing, religion-like soothing and brainwashing practice (a la Marx's description of religion as opium of people) that has been the castelessness of a casteist condition, egalitarianism of a regimented hierarchical world. A resolution (however illusory, as posterity will know) of the problems of social inequality available in the communistic collective might have won the revolutionaries away from the existing Hindu concepts of collective.

Disillusionment with the shortcomings of the revolutionary movement is recorded by Bhupendranath Dutta in his book in Bengali, *Swami Vivekananda* where Dutta records his eyewitness account of Aurobindo's "nationalist" myth making with some frustration; according to him, Aurobindo told a young revolutionary that "the monks meditating on the banks of Narmada have known by the power of *yoga* that the future emperor of India has been born in a Solar (Suryavanshiya) royal family. The revolutionaries are working by crowning him as leader" (20). As individuals living in a postmodern age, our response to how Bankim's robust intellectualism was replaced by appeals to myth and superstitions by later day nationalist intellectuals might be mixed. Aurobindo's approach was perhaps an expedient appropriation of mass psychology. National awakening was no longer contained within the intellectual phenomenon that was started by the likes of Bankim. What was earlier limited to the elite intellectuals, now spread to the masses and became a people's movement. Some problems inevitably accompanied this process.

The policy of political assassinations alienated many humanists from revolutionary nationalism. Shibram Chakraborty registers in his autobiography his experience as a teenager schoolboy recruited into a revolutionary group (such group veterans usually chose young boys as assassins to carry out operations, a practice that was morally and ethically denounced by many); he records his innocence, emotion and melancholy at being chosen as the assassin (who in turn will also be murdered on the spot by a second assassin so that police won't be able to take Shibram alive into custody) for the British Superintendent of Police. Shibram writes this episode in a way that is worthy of the greatest masters of literary art. The teenage boy finally escaped his fate of being both a martyr and a suicide in an absurdly humorous manner (99-114), but he continued his association with the nationalist movement and wrote regularly for *Jugantor*. So here was a critique of the revolutionary nationalist movement's politics of individual assassination, a critique that was just, valid, artistic and humanitarian, a critique by someone who by no means was a deserter.

M N Roy, whose original name was Narendranath Bhattacharya, was the first revolutionary who was converted to the cause of communism. It happened after he was sent abroad with some overseas assignment (regarding the Indo-German conspiracy; Narendranath was a close associate of Bagha Jatin) by the revolutionaries of Bengal, and his conversion to communism (that took place between 1917 and 1919) came at the time of high disillusionment with the national revolutionary movement in Bengal. This conversion coincided with the success of the Bolshevik capture of power in Russia. Roy had a perception of Marxism as a more comprehensive ideology in times of a general decline and desperation that prevailed among the nationalist revolutionaries as he speaks of his early association with the revolutionary nationalist movement in a dismissive tone (his following recollection appears in the anthology *Ognijug* edited by Shailesh Dey): “We were in an ambiance of a vague idealism. Many did not have any clear idea about the road and ration of life, nor was there any specific philosophical ideology. Only the supreme desire in our consciousness was this – to find a place on the pages of history as a hero, and to leave footprints on the sandy shores of time.” (2: 149).

Thus, the story of Indian Communism grew out of the loose ends of the revolutionary movement. A telos of an inevitable journey of the revolutionaries towards the destination of Marxism is carried forward by the oeuvres of the gifted Bengali playwright and intellectual of the left, Utpal Dutt. Dutt, a renowned thespian and actor, had performed this ideological and intellectual task of Indian left throughout his works, and in order to examine how this Bunyan-like narrative of *the revolutionary's progress* was conceived by the communists, we can turn to Dutt's unfinished novel “Phanshir Opekkhay”, published posthumously in a Sharodiya issue of a left-leaning Kolkata daily. It is a classic illustration of the narrative of historical determinism that communists wanted to tell about the conversion of the national revolutionary movement into scientific class struggle oriented communist movement. This novel traces this trajectory of Dhananjay, a young revolutionary from

Masterda Surjo Sen's revolutionary organization in Chittagong. The young revolutionary is in a condemned cell, living the last few days of his life with a renewed zeal only because he has discovered the intellectual and revolutionary promise of Marxism. The novel has a number of Muslim characters living in the harbour areas of Kolkata who are depicted as the harbingers of the international message of a classless, religion-less, communistic revolution. The novel employs the strategy of flashbacks, as the story is narrated through the remembrances of Dhananjay. M N Roy's *Vanguard* makes an appearance in Dutt's novel as a banned periodical which is secretly smuggled into India, and a Muslim communist character brags that it is more powerful than pistols; needless to repeat that *Vanguard* was not banned and used to be circulated through regular postal mails, as Muzaffar Ahmed himself tells us in his autobiography. Here is an example of reworked memory.

Dutt kept writing on the nationalist struggle for independence throughout his career. According to the editors of his collected works, the first play that he wrote in Bengali was *Mirkashim*, written between 1952 and '53. Mir Qasim, the Nawab of Bengal, who rebelled against the British is the protagonist of this play. The struggle of Tipu Sultan against the British is the subject of Dutt's play *Nil Shada Lal (Blue White Red)*. The title is an acknowledgment of Tipu's strategic alliance with the French, and there is an enactment of a play on French revolution at the behest of Tipu within this play. The oppressive regime of Warren Hastings after Bengal's colonization was complete and the legal murder of Maharaja Nandakumar (called Nuncomer by British) by the Chief Justice of the newly established Supreme Court at Calcutta Sir Elijah Impey form the dramatic substance of Dutt's play *Boniker Mandondo (The Merchant's Scale)*. The title is taken from a poem of Rabindranath, where he talks of the colonization of India by a mercantile British East India Company.

Tiner Toloyar (The Tin Sword) re-visits the nineteenth century emergence of nationalism (evoking Derozio's lines, "My Fallen Country, one kind wish from thee") at the backdrop of Bengali

theatre. *Titumir* is a historical play set in nineteenth century where the eponymous Islamist/Wahabist/Farazi character Titumir organizes a rebellion against the British imperialists and Hindu zamindars alike; Dutt rather anachronistically depicts him as a patriot and a fighter for independence and that is in tune with the standard left liberal version of Indian history. But Dutt's play *Neel Rokto (Blue Blood)* portrays the famous indigo rebellion of Bengal without any such idealizing agenda and the indigo farmers' rebellion (that was spearheaded by Harish Mukherjee's journal, *Hindu Patriot*) appears there without any imposition of left-liberal/idealist paradigm, making it interestingly human, sans the forced patriotism of *Titumir*. Dutt's play *Dnarao Pothikbor (Halt, Passer-by)* deals with the life and nationalist writings of Michael Madhusudan Dutt, and the indigo rebellion makes an appearance. Vidyasagar is rightly shown as an embodiment of Bengali nationalist pride, and Michael Madhusudan's *Meghnadbadh Kabyo* is justly depicted to be an allegory of India's loss of freedom. The Afghan war of independence (against British imperialism) in 1838 is the topic of Utpal's play, *Shimanto (Border)*. This play is an interesting celebration of feudal values and ethics over the capitalist-colonialist greed, hypocrisy, cowardice and brutality. The great rebellion of 1857 is Dutt's subject matter in the play *Mohabidroho (The Great Rebellion)*, while his play *Shonnyashir Torobari (The Monk's Sword)* is on the famous Sannyasi (Monks) rebellion, that once inspired Bankim Chandra to write *Anandamath*. The infamous Jallianwala Bagh massacre of 1919 is the subject matter of Dutt's eponymous play, *Jallianwalabagh*. In the very beginning of the play a narrator (a narrator who directly addresses the audience is both in tune with the *sutradhar* of Indian theatre and the *verfremdung* of Brechtian epic theatre) evokes the “roars of the pistols of Aurobinda and Barindra”, “the pistols of Bagha Jatin and his comrades at Buri Balam that challenged a British force ten times bigger”, “the attempt at an all India armed insurrection under the leadership of Rashbehari Bose, the great hero” and Congress's post-Independence attempt to erase the names of Rashbehari, Jatin Mukherjee, Surjo Sen and Subhash Chandra from the pages of history.

This play offers severe criticism of Gandhi and ends with Michael O'Dwyer's assassination by Udham Singh in 1940. Udham's final dialogue thus concludes the play, "The martyrs of Jallian, listen! The eunuch practice of arousing pity by lying helplessly with blood soaked bodies are over. Let the Indians be awakened with revolutionary vengeance by shooting at the bosom of the tyrants. Victory to armed struggle, victory to revolution, victory to revolutionary India!" Dutt's cult classic play *Kallol* evoked the memory of Naval rebellion, celebrated the valiant role of Communist Party and denounced the treachery of Congress. The play made history. Dutt had to remain silent about the treachery of Communist party in the immediate years preceding Naval rebellion, but anyway, selection of events is a writer's choice, so to say.

A very popular play of Utpal Dutt about Ognijug (the foreword written by noted dramatist Manmatha Roy literally and categorically puts a case for ognijug and and claims that the play will keep the spirit of ognijug alive) was *Ferari Fouj (The Absconding Army)*. The play opens with patriotic songs sung by the troubadour of Bengali nationalism, Mukunda Das who as a character makes a brief appearance in this play. The rest of the characters are imaginary. An Anushilan Samiti type insurrectionary group's failure is portrayed, with a subtle message in favour of mass revolutionary practice, the absence of which makes the group vulnerable, while a closed hierarchy and blind methods of secrecy are shown to be particularly prone to breaches and betrayals. Dutt's stint at *jatra* (Bengali folk theatre) led him to compose *Rifle*, another play on Ognijug that shares some of the themes of *Ferari Fouj*. Dutt wrote a play with Subhash Chandra Bose as the protagonist at the backdrop of INA, titled *Dilli Chalo (To Delhi)*; the title is taken from one of the famous slogans of INA given by Subhash Bose). Dutt wrote about the abortive attempt at organizing a mutiny among the Punjabi soldiers British Indian Army (an initiative taken by Rashbehari Bose in February 1915, renowned in history as the Ghadar conspiracy) in his play *Kripan (Sword)*.

Rashbehari Bose is the main character in this play that depicts his legendary exploits in north India before he left the country. Dutt's book of non-fictional prose *Girish Manosh* is a historical analysis of Ramkrishna-Vivekananda movement at the backdrop of Girish Ghosh's theatre, and this book is very interestingly nationalist, acknowledging the resistance of Hinduism against imperial oppression. Dutt writes, "Thus Ramkrishna told his contemporary Bengalis, 'Your dharma itself is superior, so you do not need to hang your head in shame. You are not barbaric, they (the British) are barbaric.' No one is prepared for a struggle unless one holds his head high. It was Ramkrishna's indirect and best achievement – to give back the ideological self-respect to Vivekananda and the twentieth century revolutionaries" (51). This book is remarkably pro-Hindu, though Dutt is very careful to omit, suppress and deform Bankim, the thinker who fathered Hindu revival in Bengal. There a cursory dismissal of Bankim as a Victorian middle class sentimental revisionist who wants to reduce the epic character of Krishna into a uni-dimensional "Premer Thakur" – a God of mere love (176), which is as wrong, as muddled and as false as it can get on the part of Dutt. Dutt partially quotes and thereby maliciously misquotes Bankim in order to castigate him as a superstitious person who believed in miracles (59). But the original passage of Bankim Chandra (from the nineteenth chapter of *Dharma Tattva*) talked of a miracle made by a talented human being (whose faculties have flourished because of *anushilan*; devotion, practice and exercise are together given the name of *anushilan*), entirely by *natural means* (2: 546). Historically, Bankim has been a steady target for left-liberal-universalist-Islamist slanderers, while Vivekananda mostly suffered attempts of appropriation.

Shailesh Dey's book *Ami Subhash Bolchi* records the life long inspiration that Vivekananda's writings provided for Subhash. In particular, Vivekananda's message influenced Bose at a critical moment when he chose to leave India in early 1941, a journey that led to the INA's struggle of independence (2: 46). Vivekananda was a figure of singular importance for the nationalist

revolutionary movement in Bengal, and it is but normal that communists would be anxious to appropriate him. Vivekananda's brother Bhupendranath Dutta wrote a book titled *Socialist Vivekananda* back in 1928/29. It was a socialist appropriation of Vivekananda. Bhupendranath Dutta imposes a communistic telos on Vivekananda's project. He writes in his Bengali monograph, *Swami Vivekananda*: “only one thing needs to be stated clearly that the 'national consciousness' that was awake in the age of subjugation (preceding the age of Vivekananda) was nothing but a xenophobia against the foreign rulers. The ideals and agenda of Swamiji was unthinkable for them” (19). Any reader of Bankim will realize the mistake contained in this statement. Bhupendranath himself acknowledged that Vivekananda in early teenage came under the moulding influence of Bankim's “jatiyobhavoddipak” books, that is, books which evoked national feelings (2), but apart from this, his book is silent on Bankim. It should be noted here that the influence of Bankim on Vivekananda extended beyond the latter's formative years. *Ognijug*, a compendium (in two volumes, edited by Shailesh Dey) of recollections made by nationalist revolutionaries themselves and writings on them, opens with a reminiscence of Hemchandra Ghosh, the founder of Bengal Volunteers and close associate of Subhash. He remembers meeting Swami Vivekananda in 1901, who told him in a restless manner, “Read Bankim Chandra – Bankim Chandra – and Bankim Chandra only” (1: 2). Surely Vivekananda did not mean that other thinkers and writers were not to be read. Vivekananda was physically ill, probably he realized that he was nearing his end (he died in 1902), and he might have felt a certain restlessness about the unfinished mission of his life that could only be materialized in an independent India. He was an avid nationalist, and throughout his life continued to draw inspiration from Bankim, and it is only natural that he would advise others (particularly those with a nationalist dispensation) to study Bankim in depth.

Going back to Bhupendranath's *Swami Vivekananda*, a book that attempts a communistic appropriation of Vivekananda, we see that words like class, proletariat, historical materialism and

dialectical materialism appear almost on every page, every now and then. It appears that Vivekananda underwent a purification rituals at the hands of communist ideology, in order to gain a generous accommodation within the gracious narrative of communism, where his prophecies about impending Russian and Chinese revolutions (as pointed out by Bhupendranath) somehow redeem this fallen spiritualist with an adequate materialist vigour.

Communists appropriated the Bengali revolutionaries as well. Amalendu Ghosh expresses his indignation at the over-stretched narrative that the communists wanted to tell:

But in this regard a comment made by Muzaffar Ahmed in an article titled “The Terrorist Revolutionaries Came to Communist Party” in a Sharodiya issue of *Nandan* (note: *Nandan* is CPIM's intellectual organ on art, aesthetics and ideology in Bengal) was thoroughly ludicrous. In Muzaffar Ahmed's language: “The Government of India declared the Communist Party illegal in 1934. Therefore those who were terrorists came to the Communist Party risking great hazards.” Against this statement, the comment of the eminent revolutionary leader of Jugantar Party Bhupendra Kumar Dutta is, “About whom Muzaffar Saheb is saying these words? About them, who came to the revolutionary parties thinking of the hangman's noose as an object of desire, and who used to vie with each other, saying “I shall go, I shall go” when one had to be chosen between two (for an operation)? Possibility of a fifteen day or one month imprisonment for sticking the posters of the illegal party on walls was risking great hazards for them!”

And the self gratification that used to be attained by the communists by saying that so many of the communist party members were in Andamans, as they still do and speak elaborately to their followers that leaves this truth unuttered that the prisoners indoctrinated into communist ideology were transported because of participating in nationalist armed

struggle, not for any communist activities. (*Bharote Communism* 108)

There was an immediate access to and capability of expedient falsehood for the communist party as the Indian experience shows, since in addition to God and the traditional way of life, ethics, morality and values were disposed too, and man the ultimate master of his surroundings was no longer answerable to anyone but the party. Alister McGrath comments in *Twilight of Atheism* “Soviet atheism is the true religious philosophy of modernity – a totalizing worldview which demanded that all else give way to its claims. As the history of the atheist state makes clear. This inevitably sets an agenda for repression and oppression.” (232). *The Black Book of Communism* first published in France in 1997 suggests that communism was “a tragedy of planetary dimensions”, with its total number of victims between 85 and 100 millions (McGrath 233).

There was a certain license to immorality for the communist party that might not be easily available with the (mostly God-fearing) nationalist revolutionaries. But apart from that, since the Enlightenment triumphalism that thoroughly informs classical Marxist Leninist Maoist discourses came to consider communal bonding, mutual human love, morality, ethics and values to be redundant and to be discarded as relics of a bygone feudal era, Communist movement becomes a strange mirror image of the vulgar bourgeois materialist fantasy of an exploitative world (the only subversion that occurs in this regard is the casual change of position between left and right, so to say; as the famous joke goes, capitalism is the exploitation of man by man and communism is the opposite). So end will justify the means. Truth for a communist is always party truth. No basis of humanity is left unsullied by the iron hand of the party, and every violation can be justified under the guise of the progress of history.

This is not to suggest that the communists were unique in their collaborations and the nationalist movement did not have its fair share of agent provocateurs and moles and double agents. But it was not essentially a movement of collaborators. In fact, one continuum revealed in the entire history of this period is the intrigues and workings of power, which are hidden as a result of dominant ideologies which are basically narratives (grand and otherwise). The revolution never comes, because there will always be powers which will act against mass emancipation and individuals will betray their community. In the twentieth century Bengal, betrayal was done under the name of Marxist science of revolution. For certain social-historical reasons, surrender of sovereignty to foreign interests existed as a very strong current in Bengal for a long time, longer than we usually care to think. The celebration of the West by the Bengali bhadraloks (representing the rational, pro-Enlightenment, pro-Europe currents among the radically westernized intellectual sections of the Bengalis) exists within an established tradition of collaboration. But since Bengal renaissance, we find an expression of national pride among the intellectuals (a movement of history that cannot be simply explained away by any Marxist dialectics of collaboration/resistance and that can only be understood in terms of nationalist, cultural revivalist agenda coming from within a community). The communist party's actions mark a relapse to an older phase of collaboration to a large extent.

It should be noted that the communists collaborated with the British much before the official Soviet dictum to this direction came (after the Nazi Soviet war broke out), that is, communists' collaboration with the British precedes the People's War phase. As the nationalist revolutionaries pointed out time and again in their writings, a full-fledged conversion drive was carried out within British prisons by the Communist Party, with an active aid from the British authorities during 1930s. Immediately coming to mind in this regard is the notorious Lt. Governor of Bengal (between 1932 and 1937), John Anderson (later First Viscount Waverley and Chancellor of Exchequer), who was

previously credited with brutalizing and terrorizing the independence movement in Ireland through his disreputable gang of oppressors named Black and Tan (according to Wikipedia, Black and Tan was a body of armed militia “composed largely of British World War I veterans, employed by the Royal Irish Constabulary as Temporary Constables from 1920 to 1921 to suppress revolution in Ireland. Although it was established to target the Irish Republican Army, it became notorious through its numerous attacks on the Irish civilian population”), in his capacity as the last Undersecretary for Ireland between 1920 and 1922, before the establishment of the Irish free state. In Bengal, Anderson was shot at by the revolutionaries (belonging to Bengal Volunteers) in 1934, in Darjeeling. After two years, the same Anderson sends two huge wooden boxes full of Marxist literature as a gift to the prisoners at Andaman, as Amalendu Ghosh notes (*Biplobider* 212).

Dr Parimal Ray, a prisoner from Deoli detention camp (Detention camps were meant to house non-convicted National Revolutionaries whom the government needed to keep in confinement; this particular camp at Deoli, however, became a hotbed of Communistic activities, thanks to the imperial policy) recalls that in 1934, an IB officer asked him, in a routine interrogation inside the detention camp, whether he read “communistic literature”. Ray did read them. In fact he started attending a class of Marxism inside the camp that was conducted by one co-detainee Comrade Kali Sen. But Ray did not want to further antagonize the IB officer by any more evidences of revolutionary activity, so he denied that he ever read them. What happened next surprised Parimal. The IB officer instantly replied, “Oh, that is why your ideas remain so narrow and parochial. You must read communist literature”. This is recorded in Ray's autobiographical book *Down Memory Lane*, from which Amalendu Ghosh quotes in his book (*Biplobider* 212-13). Elsewhere, Ghosh, himself a revolutionary nationalist (he was a member of Bengal Volunteers), speaks of the communist proselytes as those “[w]ho had abandoned the revolver for Marxism” (*Bharote Communism* 106). The irony of history was that while our communist forefathers were being proud of being committed, scientific

revolutionary vanguards in the worldwide struggle for liberation of the toiling masses, they were actually participating in the events of Soviet imperialism and British imperialism. Dange and Ahmed both gave away their comrades and confessed to British, but Dange's case was highlighted and it became the public reason for the break up of CPI in 1964, while Muzaffar's confession was never allowed to occupy centrestage (Ghosh: 1987: 212).

Communists' collaboration with the imperial forces of Britain and Russia is a huge subject of study, and the present article's scope does not allow us to cast more than a cursory glance in that direction. It is widely known that according to Mitrokhin Archives (volume 2), Promode Dasgupta, the leader of CPI (later CPIM) was an IB spy, a mole of the British planted into the Communist Party in its days of closeness with the British. Sunanda Sanyal and Soumya Basu's book, *The Sickle and the Crescent: Communists, Muslim League and India's Partition*, a book that chronicles the deep interrelationship between Communist Party and the Islamists, to a large extent which was a result of Soviet instructions (though balkanization of India was preferred by the British), makes a reference to the Soli Batlivala controversy that directly brought to the fore the dubious role played by the Communist Party:

Soli and his wife, Nargis Batlivala, were confirmed Communists. Disillusion with the policies followed by the Party during the War, both resigned from the CPI. Later, Soli went hammers and tongs against the Party. "I challenge Joshi", thundered Soli, "to contradict me when I say that he detained certain party members without the knowledge of the Central Committee or the rank and file of the party to be in touch with the army intelligence department and supply the CID chief with such information as they would require against nationalist workers, who were connected with the '42 Movement or against persons who had come to India on behalf of the Azad Hind Government (sic) of Netaji... As regards the 1942 Congress Workers who

carried on the struggle secretly, all party units submitted lists of such workers to the police”
(Batlivala, Soli, *Facts vs Forgery*, p9). (Sanyal and Basu 53)

Communist Party of India and the Kirti Kisan Party of Punjab both betrayed Subhash Bose in the aftermath of Germany's attack on Russia, under instructions from Russia. They divulged the names of Subhash loyalists in Bengal to the British, and as a result, most of the Bengal Volunteers leaders were immediately arrested and tortured in police custody for helping Subhash to escape. The role of the communists during this period was chronicled by Batlivala in some details. Eminent historian R C Majumdar is quoted in this connection by Amalendu Ghosh in his book *Bharote Communism*:

Batlivala added that Joshi had, as General Secretary of the Party written a letter in which he offered 'unconditional help' to then then Govt. of India and the Army G.H.Q. To fight the 1942 underground work and the Azad Hind Fauz (I.N.A.) of Subhash Chandra Bose, even to the point of getting them arrested. These men were characterized by Joshi in his letter as traitors and 'Fifth Columnists'. Joshi's letter also revealed that C.P.I. was receiving financial aid from the Govt., had secret pact with Muslim League and was undermining Congress activities in various ways. (166)

The question of foreign collaboration has been a standard charge against the communists and it became a very sensitive issue for them. Amalendu Ghosh quotes Meenu Masani in this regard: “The Indian Communists have always feigned righteous indignation at any mention of this fact [foreign aid]” (*Bharote Communism* 78).

Communist narratives were made in a manner so that nationalism, Indian identity and cultural sovereignty could be suppressed, struggle for national liberation could be diverted into class struggle,

while a class conception of society (not that such a conception is invalid) would be made to engulf the question of nation and community apropos the struggle against British imperialism. Omissions, absences and dark spots galore in the communist narratives as they are supposed not to see and not to show certain things. An example par excellence is *Nobanno*, a play that talked about the oppression of rich Bengalis on the poor ones, thus skilfully concealing the issue of national freedom. Amalendu Ghosh points out,

The play *Nobanno* authored by Bijan Bhattacharya and acted by IPTA in 1944 created a good response. Their acting skills were congratulated for being commintedly realistic. In this play, the actors were Bijan Bhattacharya, Shambhu Mitra, Tripti Mitra, Sudhi Pradhan, Charu Prakash Ghosh et at. But *Nobanno* and the other plays which IPTA later staged had only the themes of exploitation and class struggle. They presented only the country landlords, profiteers and black-marketeers as the class enemies, hiding the oppressive foreign rules from their vision. The struggle of the exploited mass was only against those indigenous class enemies, not against the British. (*Bharote Communism* 158)

People's War was at its peak. One sample communist song in Bengali from those days is quoted by Ghosh:

Comrade take up the weapon, take up the weapon

No longer alone in the freedom struggle today

Revolutionary Soviet, invincible China

With us are the British, and fearless Yankees. (*Bharote Communism* 156)

It was still not Mao's China, as Ghosh reminds us, but it was Chiang Kai Shek's Kuomintang. Clearly the communists referred to the international alliance in WWII. P C Joshi reportedly wanted to send troupes of song and dance and theatre to the border so that the soldiers fighting against Netaji's INA could be motivated into believing that while fighting for British occupation, they were really fighting out a patriotic war (Ghosh: 1987: 156). It becomes evident that communists learned what worked and what did not at a very heavy cost, only after repeated failures to sell their collaboration with British imperialism to the masses as revolutionary activities. Here is a realization that dawned on Utpal Dutt, as he records it in his treatise on revolutionary theatre (titled *Jopen-da Jopen Ja* – that is, *What Jopen-da Utters*) written in a dialogue form:

I said – Did you see? All immature brats, at most newly entered colleges. Already they have hot the road with bombs. They have to be made into heroes in theatre? They are extremists, making hindrances in revolution. .. All extremist agent provocateurs.

Jopen-da said in lazy voice – that is a political analysis. Theatre or poetry does not walk that way.

– Why ?

– When politicians seat and estimate, they find so many faults in the acts of Khudiram, Bhagat Singh and Surjo Sen which cannot be enumerated. But the people compose songs right on them, and those songs spread to different corners of the country. Those who open up the windows of the immovable palace of politics to look outside, however hard we make them guilty for their sins, the people say to them, “we give you the right to know the truth by mistake.” How everyone of you buried Subhash beneath criticisms, but the moment he took the rifle, instantly he made his lifelong dwelling in the hearts of the people. In the eyes of the people the armed revolutionaries alone are felicitated. (*Godyo Shongroho* 136)

I remember having come across a couplet of Hindi poetry (from *Saket*, written by Mythili Sharan Gupta) once. It goes like this: “Ram tumhara vrita swayam hi kavya hai,/Koi kavi ban jaye, sahaj sambhavya hai” (bridge-india.blogspot.com). The lines mean, “Ram your history/story itself is poetry/Anyone (who narrates your life) will become a poet, that is an easy possibility.” The message encoded in this couplet, that certain lives are stories of an epic scale in themselves (irrespective of who narrates the story), partly explains why Shailesh Dey's mammoth, epic length docu-fiction *Ami Subhash Bolchi* (first published serially in *Uttorath* – a popular film and entertainment magazine of yesteryears – over 36 issues) became a cult classic despite several authorial weaknesses. For example, in this novel, at one instance Surjo Sen walks like a valiant knight in armour to the gallows, the next instance he is brought to the gallows senseless because of the terrible torture of British police. Dinesh (of Benoy Badal Dinesh trio) utters *karenge ya marenge*, at the time of storming the Writers' Building, which is anachronistic. At one point Subhash is credited with causing the first switchover of loyalty among the Indian soldiers, and a little after that, Dey's novel gives detailed descriptions about Rashbehari's partially successful design of establishing networks among the soldiers. Use of cliched expressions, which is best avoided by any writer, runs riot in Dey's book. Every other line is invested with extremely hackneyed, melodramatic repetitions of slogans, jargons, wisecracks, idioms and shlokas. For example, Subhash's anxiety at the news of his father's illness is promptly explained with a Sankrit shloka, “pita swarga, pita dharma...”. It is the manifestation of an artistic profanity that might resemble the characteristics of a Jatra, that is always anxious to reach out to a mass who must be told every thing in a loud manner and things must be put in black and white.

Ami Subhash Bolchi records the entire historical sequence of Bengali revolutionary nationalism in the format of novel. This book is not just about Subhash, and the narrative goes back and forth in time to speak about the noted martyrs of Bengal. Subhash can indeed be a writer's

choice to trace the trajectory of the militant nationalism of Bengal, as Subhash's connections with the militant, revolutionary nationalists are well established. Parthasarathi Basu (in the compendium *Ognijug* edited by Shailesh Dey) speaks of British Intelligence sources that establish connections between Subhash and the Bengal “terrorists”. He quotes from the 'secret archive of police': “In 1924 the terrorist members of the Swarajya Party supported the candidature of Mr Subhas Chandra Bose as Chief Executive Officer of the Corporation and it is noteworthy that after his appointment to that post many jobs in the Corporation were given to terrorists.” Further, “[a]t this time there was an agreement between Subhas and the terrorists that the latter should run the Bengal Provincial Congress Committee under his guidance.” Moreover, “[e]arly in 1925 a prominent member of the Congress admitted during an interview with a high Government official that he knew personally of the existence in Bengal of a terrorist movement the members of which, were hand in glove with the Swarajist” (2: 237-38). Such revolutionary networks foreshadow the INA chapter of Subhash's life.

INA reminds us of Rashbehari Bose. The National Revolutionary movement was renowned for its international dimensions. Peter Heehs records the foreign influences on the Bengali revolutionaries since the days of Okakura and Nivedita with some details (68-95). Hemchandra Das Kanungo's networking and training with the anarchists of Europe is a glaring example. The Irish connection was always very distinct for the revolutionaries. When Jatin Das died after 63 days of hunger strike (a death that was refused the status of martyrdom by Gandhiji, who called it a “diabolical suicide”), condolence message was sent from Ireland, from the family of Terence McSwiney, the Irish martyr who gave up his life in a similar hunger strike. As Shailesh Dey records in *Ami Subhash Bolchi*, it read: “Family of Terence McSwiney have heard with grief and pride of the death of Jatin Das. Freedom will come” (1: 277). The aforementioned book records that Subhash was felicitated in 1936 by De Valera's government in Dublin (1: 298), and that he (Subhash) maintained a close contact with the German consul in Kolkata (2: 28). Bagha Jatin's Indo-German conspiracy was a

milestone event of Ognijug. Michael Silvestri in his book chronicles in details the Irish connection of the Bengali revolutionaries and quotes Amitav Ghosh: “The Indians were comparatively novices in the arts of sedition: it was the Irish who were their mentors and allies” (Silvestri 10). Silvestri himself suggests that Masterda Surjo Sen's Chittagong armoury raid was modeled on the Easter rising of Ireland (11). Unfortunately, what used to be a genuine international co-operation and exchange of ideas for the goal of independence changed into a blind allegiance to Russia (later China) as the revolutionary movement was hijacked by the communists.

However, it should not escape our notice that at this time, communists were emerging as the monopoly holder of revolutionary politics. Proselytizing other revolutionaries was a communist strategy not just in India. So Soviet diplomacy succeeded because it was a both way process, On one hand the Russians needed all foreign networks it could muster. On the other hand, Nationalist Revolutionaries too needed the support of foreign countries and Soviet was an inevitable choice. Even Subhash Bose acknowledged the favorable image of Soviet in the popular imagination in India and it is significant that the Azad Hind Govt, even when the situation became quite critical, refused to declare war against Soviet. In spite of all German persuasions, Subhash declared war against UK and USA only.

Koenraad Elst, a contemporary non-fictional writer both sympathetic and critical towards the cultural nationalism of India offers a very nuanced summary of the communistic conversions, and I am tempted to quote him in details:

...one important phenomenon, which was concentrated mostly in pre-Independence Bengal, viz. the shift of a large majority of revolutionaries -- particularly from the *Anushilan Samiti*

circuit -- from Nationalism to the Communist movement. An auxiliary reason for this development was British aid: revolutionary prisoners were given Marxist literature, because the British knew that the Communists opposed terrorist violence and aimed for a mass uprising in the long term, thus leaving British (and other oppressors') lives out of harm's way until the time of the Revolution, which moreover might never materialize. Hindu nationalists who easily resort to cheap blame-the-British scenarios ("Jinnah was brainwashed by the British into trading in nationalism for separatism"), tend to overplay the importance of this; the British could only reinforce a tendency already in operation. After the success of the Bolshevik revolution in 1917-20, it was but natural that activists of a revolutionary temperament worldwide would feel attracted to Marxism. At least, they did so wherever an alternative was lacking. In Italy, many joined the Fascist movement and grabbed power in 1923 on a very similar wave of revolutionary enthusiasm.

Did India have an alternative? The freedom movement was captured by M.K. Gandhi in 1920 and left no room for revolutionaries, whom Gandhi emphatically disowned and condemned. The fledgling RSS, founded by an *Anushilan Samiti* disappointment, Dr. K.B. Hedgewar, renounced politics and preferred work in the sphere of culture, social self-organization and "character building". Hedgewar rejected offers to integrate his volunteer corps with the Hindu Mahasabha in political work for national independence and for the safeguarding of Hindu interests. So, it is likely that many revolutionaries, initially motivated only by love of India and freedom, turned to Marxism not because of this ideology's intrinsic strengths, but for lack of a native ideological alternative. (koenraadelst.blogspot.com)

We need to understand that Indian communism was not simply the proverbial serpent entering Behula's nuptial room. It was a complex historical process, the outlines of which I have tried to draw in this article, I have attempted a rediscovery of *the truths of the events* of our nationalist movement

by re-reading the histories/stories/narratives/accounts/testimonies of the militant nationalists. There are certain retrospective narrative designs which left-liberal writers have tried to impose on the trajectory of our history, and I have tried to deconstruct them. And where I end, I believe, will be the take-off point where a whole new critical interest in Ognijug will be born, as we shall critically revisit this period again and again and examine its glories and its mistakes alike. As a political nationalist, I have attempted to challenge the Hobsbawm diktat and made a humble endeavor to re-establish academic nationalism at a time when India is facing huge neo-liberal and neo-colonial onslaughts which the worn out cliches of the reigning left/liberal pundits have been singularly incapable to resist.

It might baffle the vulgar materialists of both capitalist and communistic varieties that the people living in Ognijug gave up freely their lives in order to gain freedom, that is an immaterial, abstract, transcendent concept that defies all immediate material compulsions. An answer to that bafflement is not possible without taking recourse to the age old human instincts and values of ethics and morality (none of which can be adequately economical). It is here we meet another defeat of classical Marxist doctrines. It is well known that Subhash and the Bengal revolutionaries drew their tremendous moral courage from the teachings of Bankim and Vivekananda, from *Gita* and *Upanishad*. The idea of sacrifice is essentially spiritual, it dwells in the domain of ideas and instincts which have the capability to annihilate economic compulsions. Communal bonding, identity and fellow feelings can run contrary to all immediate class concerns. Partially, psychoanalysis addresses these issues. But one has to come to the questions of human identity, culture, community and dharma to understand these *events* Bengal witnessed in Ognijug.

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